

Data Analytics in IT Applications

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

There is a lot of data in the IT industry .Sometimes its even big data .These data are either used for decision making or for profit or to know which customer is better

2. Aim

How to use data analytics in IT Applications for decision making

3. Material and methods

A raw data was taken in MS Excel which has all the details of ID,Name,Age,customers,vendors,cities,or date,offboarding date.Company bought a business intelligence tool according to their budget and used excel as input.

4. Results

Using the business intelligence tool company was able to make decision based on the data visualization and dashboard which was made.

5. Conclusions

According to the results of this study, almost the IT Applications team was determine how employees onboarded and off boarded in past 3 years .Even they were able to know how many vendors ,purchase orders ,customers ,bills they had in quarterly ,Monthly and yearly basis

6. Keywords

Data Analytics; Business Intelligence; Data Visualization

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References

Author biography

Priyabrata Purohit has completed Masters degree in Engineering Management with a specialization in Information Systems and Data Analytics from Northeastern University, Boston at the age of 25. Priyabrata also holds a bachelor in technology from VIT University, Vellore, India. Priyabrata is currently Process Specialist - data at Google India via Cognizant Technology Solutions. Priyabrata has worked in both India and USA in startups and big corporates.